

Sample ID **3-4 (Combined)**

Operator ID **user**

Notes

Elapsed Time	00:01:00
Median Diam.	57.4 nm
Mean Diam.	66.7 nm
Polydispersity	0.351
GSD	1.730

Lognormal Size Distribution

d(nm)	G(d)	C(d)	d(nm)	G(d)	C(d)	d(nm)	G(d)	C(d)
23.3	26	5	50.0	97	40	83.0	80	75
28.4	44	10	53.6	99	45	91.1	70	80
32.5	58	15	57.4	100	50	101.3	58	85
36.2	70	20	61.5	99	55	115.9	44	90
39.7	80	25	65.9	97	60	141.4	26	95
43.1	87	30	70.9	93	65			
46.5	93	35	76.5	87	70			